
**Anthropogenic Pressure Influences On Waders Habitat During Summer
On Bargaon Reservoir Near Yavatmal City, Maharashtra.**

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Abstract:

The Bargaon Dam is a Medium project and is protected for the main purpose of fish production and irrigation. The fish capacity of this dam is good. A large number of migrants and local bird species have been recorded on the dam. During the winter and summer seasons i.e. from October to May, many Ducks and Geese species, various types of Terns, Gulls, Plovers, Sandpipers, Shanks, Stints, Stilts, Godwit, Spoonbill, Storks, Wagtails, Herons, Egrets, Lapwings, Pipits and Pratincole are easily seen. Total 110 waders including migratory and residential were sighted with countable numbers in the beginning but in the last couple years almost 88 waders are recorded with very less numbers. The observatory records particularly in the summer from 2016 to 2024 reveals that the wetland and surrounding grassland of reservoir is highly disturbed due to anthropogenic pressure like cultivation on large wetland area, Soil Excavation near water and grassland, number of Diesel pumps on every possible sites, Cattle grazing and numbers of scary dogs movement which directly affects on wetland habitat and the results are decrease the number of migratory waders and most of them were irregularly sighted for very short period, feeding activity is disturbed, breeding ground are destroyed, and percentage of bird poaching tremendously high, if serious action should not be taken for the conservation of wetland then Bargaon reservoir loses their birding hotspot identity because most of the migratory species would not be visited and residential species are migrated.

Keywords: Bargaon Dam, Anthropogenic Pressure, Waders Habitat, Summer.

Introduction:

Wetland ecosystems are important by several ways like conserving, protecting and improving water quality. It provides habitat for a diversified variety of species starting from microbes and continuing to aquatic plants, water insects, amphibians, reptiles, birds, fishes and mammals. They provide great volumes of food that attract many species, especially birds. Majority of invertebrate and vertebrate species depend on wetland for food, water and shelters. They can help by storing flood waters and the most important thing is maintaining surface water level in the surrounding area. Now a days anthropogenic activities cause alteration of physical, chemical and biological components of wetland

ecosystems. Majority of wetland degrades and loses by changing water quality, increasing pollutants inputs, changing species composition, catchment degradation, soil excavation, Industry and agricultural benefits. Present study highlights anthropogenic pressure effects on waders survival and problems particularly in summer of Bargaon reservoir near Yavatmal city.

Material and Methods:

Bargaon dam is an irrigation project constructed by Government of Maharashtra in 1993 which is built on a compound local Nallah. It is situated on 20°26'57" N 78°11'28" E North east direction which is 11

km from Yavatmal city. The length is 830 m and live storage capacity

12.224 MCM.

Image-1 (Satellite View of Borgaon Reservoir)

There are no intentional visits arranged because during summer from February up to May repeatedly visited for waders study. The observatory data with photographic evidence were collected in relation to anthropogenic interferences. During study period i.e. from February 2016 to May 2024 visited more than hundred time in the morning hours and photographic records were taken by the help of DSLR d7500 Nikon camera with the lens 200-500 Nikkor.

Result:

Borgaon reservoir is a medium project mainly constructed for irrigation but it is also given on lease to the fishermen society for Pisciculture. The canal fulfilled water demand and benefitted large agricultural area. The status of Pisciculture

is satisfactory which helps to improve the economic status of fishermen in the area. The regular visits were started in the year 2006 for ornithology study mainly waders. The wetland fulfilled all the demands of water birds like food, shelter, roosting and breeding. In the year 2015 water birds count in thousands and more than 110 variety waders species sighted on Borgaon. The condition could drastically change from summer 2016 and it is adverse in 2024. The anthropogenic pressure could be started with excavation of soil but a very limited and specific area now once the water level is decreased every possible way should be adapted even the JCB is used to excavate the soil deeply up to the exposed rocky area. There is a permanent loss of habitat in these regions.(Photo-1)

Photo-1- Excavation of Soil with help of JCB

Photo-2- Cultivation on Wetland in Summer

Photo-3- Little Chicks of Kentish Plover

Photo-4- Cattle grazing throughout the day on grassland.

Photo-5-Feral dogs eat wader eggs

Second cause affects more because up to the year 2014 there was no cultivation on the acquired land around the reservoir so when the water level decreases a very wetland and grassland were developed. Large number of waders were counted with a great diversity. It was noticed that from the year 2016 during monsoon the water level increases. At that time there was no cultivation but once the water level decreased in the winter farmers used to sow wheat and gram on that land. What's even scarier is that as the water recedes in the summer these people would sow jowar or maize in those wetland. As you see in the photo, these people have planted crops even in summer, right up to the water. (Photo-2) Unfortunately year after year this condition is horrible now there are no wetland and grassland remains ultimately waders diversity and their number decreases. In this area numbers of wader like Little ring plover, Kentish plover, Small Pratincole,

Thick-knee and lapwings successfully breed but there are no breeding grounds remaining. (Photo-3) seven to eight years ago from the month of February water level started to decrease and in April big grassland and a very wetland were developed. Returning migratory waders and residential birds have a big area for feeding and roosting and the large grassland is available for cattle's to graze. Farmers use most of the area for fodder cultivation in summer and very few areas remain for cattle grazing. (Photo-4) Farmers have dogs in the field and dogs coming with cattle's. All day they are roaming throughout wetland and grassland searching for waders eggs. This is one of the reasons that successful breeding could not be possible.(Photo-5)

Along with these reasons other problems like continuous noise of diesel pumps in the wetland, excessive fishing and fishermen movements

particularly in the morning hours causing trouble to the waders.

Discussion:

Worldwide data said that fifty to sixty percent of the waders population has declined. Considering waders data of last sixteen from yavatmal clearly indicated that the diversity and population consistently decline. Anthropogenic pressure increases the decline in the number of waders on Borgaon reservoir. If a few steps are positively implemented it helps to improve the habitat and automatically increases the diversity of migratory and residential waders.

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